

LEARNING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE AT SCHOOL

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Abstract:

The main aim of this article is highlight the importance of learning English as a second language at school. Teaching methods are related to learners' academic achievement, especially with learners with reading problems. Therefore there is need to establish teaching approaches /strategies teachers employ in teaching of reading in school settings.

Key words: learning English, ESL learners, second language, grade levels, working collaboratively, techniques.

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Students for whom English is a second language are growing day by day. All districts have felt the impact of this growth, and the need to provide appropriate English Second Language service is becoming an issue for district in all areas. Settlement patterns throughout the province reflect enormous diversity. Some school districts have only a few ESL learners scattered throughout their schools. Others have significant enrolments of first students, some of whom many be identified as ESL learners. Some school districts, which account for 90% of provincial ESL enrolment, have a number of schools in which ESL students represent a significant proportion of the student population. Each of these situations is complex and demanding in its own way.

Second language learning indicates that ESL students in the English-speaking school system require appropriate English language support. Educators have the responsibility of promoting the equitable participation of ESL students in schools. A clear understanding of ESL students and their needs is a prerequisite if the school system is to enable them to develop their individual potential.

While classroom teachers share in the responsibility for educating ESL students, the ESL specialist has specialized training in the field of English as a second language, and is qualified to help make initial assessment, placement, and programming decisions. The specialist teacher is also able to provide information on the linguistic, cultural, academic, and social adjustment of ESL students at all ages and grade levels. This guide has been produced with the input of ESL specialist across the province. It is intended to assist ESL specialist teachers, including district consultants, school based teachers, or itinerant teachers who work with students in several different schools.

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It is a good idea for the teacher responsible for welcoming the student, or an assigned peer, to take the new ESL student on a tour of the school. The student can visit the classroom, see the location of the washroom, gym, and library, and meet classmates and staff members. Schools are encouraged to create an orientation package of information that all students will find useful. Depending on the ESL student's understanding of English, classroom routines, rules, or supplies can also be discussed. Conversation with the learner in this informal setting encourages the use of whatever English the student knows. However, it is important that this not be considered part of any formal judgment or assessment.

New students need time to absorb the sights and sounds around them, to get used to the school routine, and to become comfortable in their new classroom. An ideal orientation program also provides a buddy from the English-speaking mainstream group. With their buddies to answer their questions and the opportunity to watch and listen in a warm, supportive atmosphere, new students soon are ready for the next step—beginning to participate whenever they can. During any ESL assessment, the following points need to be kept in mind: English language proficiency includes both receptive English and expressive English. Receptive language is usually more extensive than expressive. Recent trends in language assessment are towards assessment instruments which integrate these various channels and skill areas, and which include at least some pragmatic assessment. English language proficiency should be considered in broad terms to take account of the differences between language used for communication in social settings and language used for academic learning in all content areas. Topics addressed in the initial assessment should include subject-specific academic language.

It is not secret that there is an important role of teachers in teaching language. With regard to meeting the needs of EL learners, the kind of support that evolves will depend on a high degree on the ESL teacher. A well-trained ESL teacher is a powerful catalyst in providing strong and effective service delivery. It is part of the role of the specialist to advocate for and provide in working toward equitable access for the learner.

Working collaboratively with subject-area or grade-level teachers is part of the ESL specialist's role. What follows is a synopsis of a few of the cooperative strategies/techniques that specialist teachers tried over a two-year period. The strategies used are by no means an exhaustive list. No particular approach is more valid than any other but rather needs to be chosen and adapted as appropriate within the context of the school and within the comfort level of the teachers involved. These techniques are listed in order of increasing interdependence, that is, requiring more and more cooperation and joint work to facilitate the process.

Increase comfort levels:

Simple lunchroom conversations can lead to discussions of possible ways to work together to assist specific learners. Everyone feels more comfortable if they feel they know colleagues as individuals, perhaps share common interest, etc. Going to someone's room to get a progress report on a student is another informal way to start conversations about possible strategies.

Share expertise can go a long way. Based on rapport established in conversation, you might be able to offer to share materials that you know work,

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especially when a teacher indicated a need to find appropriate materials for that topic. This can be the gateway for future collaborative efforts.

Do a demonstration lesson:

Teachers often complain about the students not “getting” a particular concept. Volunteering or complying with a request to demonstrate teaching that concept in a way that will assist everyone in the class, including the ESL learners can become a first step to further work together.

Mentor new teacher:

New teachers tend to be only too pleased to have an opportunity to benefit from those willing to share both materials and techniques. Currently, those who have been in the profession for a long time benefit from new ideas and the boundless enthusiasm and energy of the new teachers on staff. Making the first move is the key.

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